

A data-centric platform for scientific support to EU policies

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ABSTRACT

The Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission has set up the JRC Big Data Analytics Platform (BDAP). This paper presents the ecosystem composed of APIs, ad-hoc libraries, tools and services that allow data scientists to easily access, analyse, view, and reuse scientific data for producing and communicating policy relevant results.

1. THE BIG DATA ANALYTICS PLATFORM

The role of the Joint Research Centre (JRC)¹ of the European Commission is to provide independent, evidence-based science and knowledge, supporting European Union (EU) policies to positively impact society. This requires combining data and expertise across scientific domains. In this context, the JRC has developed a data platform to help linking data, data scientists, and thematic experts in order to generate enhanced policy-relevant insights. The name of this platform is JRC Big Data Analytics Platform (BDAP)² (Soille, et al., 2018).

In the latest years, an increasingly amount of free data has been made available from many different sources. In particular, geospatial data from projects such as Landsat (by the United States Geological Survey - USGS) or Sentinel (by the Copernicus Earth observation and monitoring program of the European Union) provide huge amount of data, in the order of terabytes each day. These data are used by researchers in many different contexts related to environment, climate change, crisis management, and sustainable development goals.

For a proper and simple usage by researchers, these data need to undergo a series of steps, from download to data curation. BDAP aims of taking care of these steps for geospatial and other sources of data. For this, BDAP downloads, cleans, and curates massive datasets on commodity hardware disks. The storage is then directly coupled with processing nodes to avoid any bottleneck when performing data analytics. The entire ecosystem is based on open-source resources.

BDAP also provides to its users, mostly researchers of the EU, a series of tools to work on these datasets: Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) to search and retrieve data, ad-hoc libraries to operate on it, and several environments allowing for applications such as simple

(¹) https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/index_en

(²) <https://jeodpp.jrc.ec.europa.eu/bdap/>

investigations, high-throughput computing, deep learning analysis, and interactive visualizations.

This paper focuses on the journey of data inside BDAP, from download, to cataloguing, and finally usage (and possibly re-usage). In Chapter 2 the data journey in BDAP will be introduced; all its steps will be then further described in Chapters 3, 4, and 5, while Chapter 6 will draw some conclusions.

2. A DATA STORY IN BDAP

Figure 1. A data story in BDAP, from the download to the final user.

This Chapter gives an overview of the data journey inside BDAP, from the download, all the way to the final usage.

Its steps can be split into three macro-areas: data ingestion, data browsing, and data use.

2.1. Data Ingestion

The first area is directly taken care of by the BDAP team. When there is the need for data (e.g. a user's request), a dedicated download and ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) procedure is created. Data is then validated, stored in commodity hardware disks located in-house, and catalogued.

2.2. Data Browsing

BDAP provides various applications and tools to query, discover, and visualize the available data. These tools are based on REST APIs. They include a web data catalogue and visualization tools to explore and interact with the data itself. Obviously, users can directly use the APIs to create custom queries and promptly access data.

2.3. Data Use

Once data has been located, users have a number of tools in BDAP to use it (e.g., access it, process it, or display results). BDAP proposes several environments adapted to the user needs. Among others, a remote desktop terminal service, a Jupyter notebook environment, a batch processing service, and GPU-based servers for deep learning tasks. BDAP also provides ad-hoc libraries, based on the aforementioned APIs, which can be used to manipulate data, in addition to many open-source resources available.

Users are encouraged to share the data products they generate, which can be afterwards managed as any other data source following the pipeline in *Figure 1*.

3. DATA AND METADATA INGESTION

Data ingestion in BDAP depends on users' needs and covers data from various domains, including elevation, soil, land cover, population, meteorological, and hydrography, among others. BDAP has various micro-services focused on separate phases of the data ingestion process. These micro-services can be reused and combined into different workflows depending on the input data and on its provider. Recurrent downloads can be scheduled at specific time intervals and various data validations and quality checks can be performed. All logs are collected and pushed into a log monitoring system where specific alerts are set for automatically checking the whole ingestion process.

Once data are considered valid, they are stored in commodity hardware disks located in an in-house data centre. This petabyte-scale storage is managed through EOS³, an open-source distributed file system developed by CERN (Peters, Sindrilaru, & Adde, 2015). Finally, data are catalogued through semi-automatic production of JSON metadata, which are then stored in an Elasticsearch⁴ instance.

Since most data have a location and a time stamp, the standard chosen for metadata is STAC⁵, an open specification that is gaining traction for cataloguing spatio-temporal data. STAC is a modular standard that permits to describe each data with a basic set of metadata, plus a variable number of other fields coming from various STAC extensions⁶. This permits to choose the level of detail needed for each data. The flexibility of this standard is leveraged by the flexibility of the NoSQL database Elasticsearch that allows to define various data indexes having the main fields in common, but differing one another in the domain-specific fields. Therefore, it is possible to query all these indexes at the same time through an index pattern and get the needed records from all the involved indexes. The resulting set of records will provide varying levels of details depending on the Elasticsearch index from which it was extracted.

⁽³⁾ <https://eos-web.web.cern.ch/eos-web/>

⁽⁴⁾ <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch/>

⁽⁵⁾ <https://stacspec.org>

⁽⁶⁾ <https://stac-extensions.github.io/>

The STAC standard has been chosen not only because it is very flexible but also because it is surrounded by a whole ecosystem⁷ of libraries, tools and clients that can be used out of the box for accessing and processing data. We will discuss this more in detail in Chapter 5.

To give some numbers of the ready-to-use data hosted in BDAP, the number of collections is around 400, from more than 20 different domains and from more than 100 different providers. For each collection, many datasets are available and, for specific cases such as Copernicus Sentinel data, the number of metadata records can arrive up to 20 million and correspond to about 10 petabytes of data.

4. DATA DISCOVERY, EXPLORATION, AND VISUALIZATION

All data ingested in BDAP are available in a web data catalogue⁸ (see *Figure 12*) based on the Open-Source software STAC browser⁹. Users can browse each collection and its related items and can search for data from a specific time-range and/or spatial extent (see *Figure 3*). Once users locate a specific dataset, they can explore it through a fully-fledged geospatial application called Collection Explorer¹⁰ (see *Figure 4*). This application allows users to interact with any geospatial dataset, compose a map by fusing raster and vector layers coming from different data collections, define their symbology and generate temporal profiles and videos for better comprehension of natural phenomena.

These applications use standard STAC REST APIs¹¹ that are based on stac-fastapi¹². For basic users, the searches can be simple and only require filling in basic parameters such as time range and bounding box. However, for advanced users, searches can be more complex by composing a JSON query using various metadata parameters, combined with ordering and pagination. Elasticsearch REST APIs are well-suited for this type of behaviour and can effectively leverage the search capabilities provided by STAC APIs.

BDAP users can easily locate the necessary documentation to utilize these APIs and interpret the metadata returned, thanks to the STAC community documentation¹³. Additionally, they can rely on an internationally recognized standard that enables their analysis and processing to be easily reused in other systems or environments that use STAC.

(7) <https://stacindex.org/ecosystem/>

(8) <https://jeodpp.jrc.ec.europa.eu/eu/data/stac-browser/> (EU Login authentication needed)

(9) <https://github.com/radiantearth/stac-browser/>

(10) <https://jeodpp.jrc.ec.europa.eu/eu/dashboard/voila/render/CollectionsExplorer/CollectionsExplorer.ipynb>
(EU Login authentication needed)

(11) <https://jeodpp.jrc.ec.europa.eu/eu/data/stac-api/api.html> (EU Login authentication needed)

(12) <https://github.com/stac-utils/stac-fastapi/>

(13) <https://github.com/radiantearth/stac-spec/>

EUMETSAT Data
in JRC Big Data Analytics Platform Catalog

Go to Parent Browse

Source Share

Description
EUMETSAT Collections available in the JRC Big Data Analytics Platform (BDAP).

Collections 8 Tiles List Ascending Descending

Filter catalogs by title

MSG Daily Surface Albedo (MDAL, LSA-101)

The MDAL albedo product is generated each day at the full spatial resolution of the MSG/SEVIRI instrument. An iterative scheme allows the...

1/1/2004, 12:00:00 AM UTC - 12/31/2021, 11:59:59 PM UTC

MSG Daily Fraction of Vegetation Cover (MDFVC, LSA-421)

Fractional Vegetation Cover (FVC) defines an important structural property of a plant canopy, which corresponds to the complement to unity of...

1/19/2004, 12:00:00 AM UTC - 12/31/2021, 11:59:59 PM UTC

MSG Downward Surface Shortwave Flux (MDSSF, LSA-201)

The Downward Surface Shortwave Flux (DSSF) refers to the radiative energy in the wavelength interval [0.3 μm, 4.0 μm] reaching the Earth's surface per...

1/19/2004, 12:00:00 AM UTC - 12/31/2021, 11:59:59 PM UTC

EUMETSAT Solar Surface Radiation Data Set - Heliosat (SARAH-2.1) Surface direct irradiance (SID)

The name SARAH stands for Solar Surface Radiation Data Set - Heliosat. In other words, solar radiation. SARAH contains data from January 1983 to...

1/1/2005, 12:00:00 AM UTC - 12/31/2020, 11:59:59 PM UTC

Figure 2. BDAP catalogue showing meteorological data from EUMETSAT.

Search
in JRC Big Data Analytics Platform Catalog

Source Share Language: English

Temporal Extent
2/2/2023 - 2/2/2023
All times in Coordinated Universal Time (UTC).

Spatial Extent
Filter by spatial extent

Collections
Select option

Item IDs
Select one or multiple item IDs...

Items per page
12
Number of items requested per page, max. 10000 items.

Filter Reset

Items

First Previous Next

S2A_MSIL1C_20230202T101231_N0509_R022_T325P9_20230202T121040.SAFE 2/2/2023, 10:12:31 AM UTC Directory JPEG 2000 Image	S2A_MSIL1C_20230202T101231_N0509_R022_T32TMM_20230202T121040.SAFE 2/2/2023, 10:12:31 AM UTC Directory JPEG 2000 Image	S2A_MSIL1C_20230202T101231_N0509_R022_T32TNN_20230202T121040.SAFE 2/2/2023, 10:12:31 AM UTC Directory JPEG 2000 Image
S2A_MSIL1C_20230202T101231_N0509_R022_T325QJ_20230202T121040.SAFE 2/2/2023, 10:12:31 AM UTC Directory JPEG 2000 Image	S2A_MSIL1C_20230202T101231_N0509_R022_T32TMM_20230202T121040.SAFE 2/2/2023, 10:12:31 AM UTC Directory JPEG 2000 Image	S2A_MSIL1C_20230202T101231_N0509_R022_T32TNN_20230202T121040.SAFE 2/2/2023, 10:12:31 AM UTC Directory JPEG 2000 Image
S2A_MSIL1C_20230202T101231_N0509_R022_T32TMK_20230202T121040.SAFE 2/2/2023, 10:12:31 AM UTC Directory JPEG 2000 Image	S2A_MSIL1C_20230202T101231_N0509_R022_T32TNK_20230202T121040.SAFE 2/2/2023, 10:12:31 AM UTC Directory JPEG 2000 Image	S2A_MSIL1C_20230202T101231_N0509_R022_T32TNP_20230202T121040.SAFE 2/2/2023, 10:12:31 AM UTC Directory JPEG 2000 Image

Figure 3. BDAP catalogue showing the search functionality.

Figure 4. BDAP data visualisation tool showing Sentinel 2 data from a specific period and a specific spatial extent.

5. DATA ACCESS, PROCESSING, AND RE-USE

BDAP provides several fully managed tools and environments to access, analyse and process the available data, according to the users' needs. The main advantage of using the BDAP environment is that these processing nodes are located within the BDAP infrastructure and therefore with fast connection to the EOS file system. Some of these processing nodes are equipped with Graphical Processing Units, mostly meant for machine learning and deep learning tasks.

The main entry point for accessing BDAP is a linux-based remote desktop environment. This environment contains or gives access to several pre-installed libraries and tools, almost entirely open-source, ranging from programming languages like Python, R, Octave and Julia, to software for geospatial analysis (QGIS, Monteverdi, gdal ...) to databases (postgres, mongodb, timescaledb), to tools for interactive processing (Jupyter Notebooks). See Figure 6 for an overview of available tools. Additional ad-hoc software can be installed directly by the users or by the BDAP administrators upon request.

BDAP also provides an environment based on HTCondor (Thain, Tannenbaum, & Livny, 2005) that exploits more than 1000 cores for high-throughput computing, which is useful to perform parallel computing over different parts of the same data.

Although, thanks to the software stack based on open-source standards, users can employ publicly available libraries. Nevertheless, BDAP provides also some ad-hoc libraries, meant to fully exploit the platform uniqueness.

The first one is `vois`¹⁴, a Python library to simplify the creation of Voilà dashboards¹⁵. It contains functions and classes that allow for fast development of data analytics dashboards, which make use of the data stored on BDAP.

Figure 5. A dashboard developed using `vois` library.

Another example is `pyjeo`¹⁶, a library for image processing for geospatial data. As already stated earlier, publicly available libraries such as `pystac` or `odc-stac` can also be used.

Figure 6. BDAP Software Landscape.

⁽¹⁴⁾ <https://vois.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁽¹⁵⁾ <https://github.com/voila-dashboards/voila>

⁽¹⁶⁾ <https://pyjeo.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have presented the JRC Big Data Analytics Platform. BDAP collects data from different sources and makes them available to EU researchers and data scientists who use it on a daily basis.

BDAP handles data storage, validation, and cataloguing, to ensure standardized and easy access to the data, using a fully open-source ecosystem.

Additionally, BDAP offers platform-specific libraries and environments to facilitate researchers in accessing, processing, and displaying data. In summary, BDAP is a fully-fledged infrastructure for generating value from data.

7. BIBLIOGRAPHY

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